

Financial Intermediation and Economic Development in Nigeria

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Recognizing that increase in output, a measure of economic growth does not always translate into improved living standard, a measure of economic development in most developing economies including Nigeria, the study set out to examine the nature of relationship that exists between financial intermediation and economic development of Nigeria. Gross Domestic Product Per Capita (GDPPC), a proxy for economic development constitutes the dependent variable, while Deposit Rate (DEPR), Lending Rate (LDNR), Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), Savings Mobilization (SAV) and Credit Extension (CRE) from 1981 to 2022 proxies for financial intermediation process and represent the explanatory variables of the study. With secondary data sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria's (CBN's) Statistical Bulletin and World Bank Data, the study (with the help of E-Views 10) applied the Johansen Co-integration, the Error Correction Model (ECM) as well as Pairwise Granger Causality Tests for analyses. From our findings, credit extension showed a statistically significant impact on gross domestic product per capita even in the current period. However, the relationship is negative. On the other hand, the results showed that monetary policy rate and lending rate are not significant in explaining changes in economic development. In view of this, the study concluded that there exists a mixed outcome on the effect of financial intermediation on economic development in Nigeria. Consequently, it is recommended that the monetary authority should persuade deposit money banks to reduce the current interest rate spread by a commensurate increase in the deposit rates. This would afford individuals especially in the rural areas the willingness to lodge in their surplus funds in expectation of high return; consequently, improving significantly financial inclusion rate as the level of domestic savings would increase.

Key Words: Economic Development, Financial Intermediation, GDPPC, Johansen Cointegration, the Error Correction Model, Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

INTRODUCTION

Traditionally, Financial intermediation is seen as a veritable tool for expanding and enhancing the productive capacity and potential of an economy. Thus, there is consensus in argument that the phenomenon appears as the tool that could help to accelerate the achievement of macroeconomic objective enhancing the living standard of the populace which is evident in equitable distribution of income, stimulating indigenous entrepreneurship especially micro, small and medium scale enterprises (MSMEs), full employment, technological development and equilibrium balance of payment. There is a symbiotic

relationship as posited by Onodugo, Kalu and Anowor (2013) existing between needed funds to the real sector and the speed of growth of an economy. The essential task of the financial system is to reposition financial resources from the surplus spending economic units to the deficit spending economic units in order to bring into being goods and services and as well to make investments in new equipment and facilities so as to stimulate the growth of the economy and improve the standard of living of citizens (Onodugo, Kalu & Anowor, 2013). Financial development connotes advancement in

the performance of financial intermediation, greater diversification opportunities, enriched information quality and better incentives for prudent lending and monitoring (Ewetan & Okodua, 2013; Alege & Ogunrinola, 2008).

From theoretical literature, the assumption of a simple financial intermediation is typical of households (surplus spending units) having financing capacity and firms (deficit spending units) having financing needs. Therefore, financial intermediation is an act of mobilizing financial resources from depositors (savers) by banks and non-banks financial institutions and channeling (lending) same to eligible borrowers over a specified period at specified rate. It involves making payments for customers, transfer and guarantees on behalf of their customers. The institutions according to Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN, 2018) that carry out the intermediaries are banks, micro-credit firms, insurance firms, pension funds, leasing companies, etc. The informal has no formalized institutional framework, no formal structural rates and comprises of local Money Lenders, Thrifts, Savings and Loans associates and all forms of Thrift associations (Onodugo, Anowor & Ofoegbu, 2018)

From the above, credits from the financial intermediaries should enhance the productive capacity of firms and strengthen their potentials to help grow the economy. This ideally captured the supply-led hypothesis which argued that the activities of financial institutions as financial intermediaries serve as useful tool for increasing the productive capacity of an economy (Olowofeso, Adeleke, & Udoji, 2015; Onodugo, Anowor, Ukwani, & Ibiam, 2014; Gerschenkron, 1962). This implies that the role of the financial system through financial intermediaries predicted on the fact that it acts as an engine of growth by broadening domestic production base, expanding the export base, narrowing the inequality gap, reducing the unemployment rate, abetting the escape from poverty trap and sustaining the growth process. The ability of an economy as argued by Mahran (2012) to mobilize financial resources to ensure easy access by investors has much to do with sustaining long-term economic growth and development. However, this appears not to be so with Nigerian economy (Agbarakwe, Anowor & Ikue, 2018; Mahran, 2012; Alege & Ogunrinola, 2008; Alenoghena, Enakali-Osoba & Mesagan (2014).

Theoretically, in financial intermediation process, financial institutions mobilize investment funds and ensure their efficient allocation, reduce risk by providing liquidity insurance, allow an efficient risk pooling among various investment projects and enrich information asymmetries to achieve efficiency in screening and monitoring investment projects. Some scholars forthrightly disagreed with the theoretical postulations that the activities of financial intermediaries in the financial system spur economic growth. Levin, Loayza and Beck (2000), Allen and Ndikumana (1998) and Korkmaz (2015) particularly questioned the status and role of financial

intermediaries in spurring and stimulating economic growth. Robinson (1952) argued that financial system does not impel economic growth rather it simply responds to development in the real sector. Shan (2005), Zang and Kim (2007) found in separate studies that financial sector has insignificant influence on economic growth and that there is no evidence of strong causal link between them. On the contrary, there is considerable evidence that financial intermediation could be essential for growth. For instance, Hassan, Sanchez and Yu (2011), Bangake and Eggoh (2011) found in individual studies that there is a strong long-run connection between financial intermediation and economic growth. Hassan, Sanchez and Yu (2011) further found out that there exists bi-directional causality between financial intermediation and economic growth among Sub-Saharan African countries.

The empirical link between financial intermediation and economic growth has long been a subject of intense scrutiny. However, it is too hasty to uphold any of the views either for financial intermediation spurring economic growth or against as even shown in the theoretical foundation. For this study, the major concern is that whatever change resulted from financial intermediation should be reflected in the economic performance of the said economy. In other words, the citizenry should be better off tangibly as a result of the gain from financial intermediation. It would seem that there are yet to be studies that had examined how financial intermediation affects output per capita (as a proxy for economic development) as well as the direction of casualty between them. Given these concerns, this study therefore is an attempt to explore the empirical nature of the linkage between financial intermediation and economic development in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Framework

There are a number of theories that underpin financial intermediation-economic development nexus. Some of these include: The theory of financial intermediation, financial repression theory, loan pricing theory, firm characteristics, theory of multiple lending etc. For the purpose of this paper, we narrow down to the theory of financial intermediation and financial repression theory.

The Theory of Financial Intermediation

This theory is predicated on the intermediation functions of Banks and their influence on economic development. Joseph Schumpeter argued in 1911 that the services provided by financial intermediaries - mobilizing savings, evaluating projects, managing risk, monitoring managers, and facilitating transactions by extending mobilized

savings as credits to the deficit economic units -stimulate technological innovation and economic development.

Financial Repression Theory

This is associated with the work of Mckinnon (1973) and Shaw (1973). The theory emphasizes that financial development would contribute most significantly to economic growth if the authorities were not to interfere in the operations of the financial institutions. According to the proponents of the theory, poor performance by banks and other financial institutions is thus often attributed to interest rate regulation, ceiling on deposit and loan rates and official guidelines pertaining to lending operations. Such interferences result in a low and often negative real case of return on financial assets and therefore inefficient savings mobilized and channeled into investment projects. To this end, the theorists advocated a positive real interest rate and financial liberalization which would ensure an optimal financial structure for development as well as eliminating the fragmentation of market. It is on these premises that this study chooses also to base its theoretical framework on the financial repression hypothesis (Udoka, 2015).

Empirical Review

Empirical evidence on the impact of financial intermediation on economic development remains inconclusive and subject to debate. Series of empirical studies has been conducted on the subject matter from both developed and developing countries for example; (Akpansung & Babalola, 2011; Murty, Sailaja & Dismisic, 2012; Muhsin & Eric, 2000; Mishra, Das & Pradhan 2009; Aliero, Abdullahi & Adamu, 2013; Hassan, Sanchez & Yu, 2011; Eatzaz & Malik, 2009; Debray, 2003; Aurangzeb, 2012; Ekpenyong & Ikechukwo, 2011). Some studies found positive relationship between commercial bank credit and the economy (Ahmed, 2008; Akpansung and Babalola 2011; Aurangzeb, 2012;) among others, while others found a negative relationship between commercial bank credit and economy (Nuno, 2012; Debray, 2003; Ekpenyong & Ikechukwo, 2011; Hassan et al. (2011), Levine (1997) and Levine, Loayza & Beck, 2000). However, the divergence in previous findings may be attributed to differences in methodologies, economic factors and time frame among others.

Akpansung and Babalola's (2011) study highlighted a positive association between private sector credit and economic growth. However, a counterproductive factor emerged—lending interest rates were identified as a hindrance to growth. This dual dynamic emphasizes the nuanced interplay of factors influencing the impact of credit on economic development in specific regional and national contexts.

Modebe, Ugwuegbe, and Ugwuoke (2014) conducted a thorough investigation into the impact of bank credit. Their findings uncovered a notable long-run relationship, revealing a negative correlation between the country's GDP and total bank credit to the private sector. This suggests a complex interplay between credit dynamics and economic performance, with potential implications for long-term growth trajectories. Contrastingly, Marshall, Igbani, and Onuegbu's (2015) study offered a different perspective, revealing a robust and positive correlation between bank credit and GDP in Nigeria. This positive association underscores the potential role of credit as a catalyst for economic expansion, emphasizing the intricate dynamics at play in Nigeria's financial and economic spheres.

Ganiyu et al.'s (2017) empirical investigation of the Nigerian economy yielded a significant finding that credit serves as a growth-enhancing factor, demonstrating its resilience even under challenging conditions. This insight underscores the crucial role of credit in stimulating economic development, providing a counterpoint to concerns about adverse economic conditions. In a related exploration, Akani and Onyema (2017) delved into the determinants of credit growth in Nigeria. Their study identified macroeconomic variables with substantial impacts, shedding light on the multifaceted factors influencing the dynamics of credit expansion. This nuanced understanding contributes valuable insights to policymakers and researchers seeking to navigate the complexities of credit-related phenomena in the Nigerian economic context.

Idachaba, Olukotun, and Elam's (2019) meticulous study intricately explored the interplay between bank credits and the Nigerian economy. Within this nuanced landscape, their findings uncovered a positive influence when credit was directed to the private sector. In contrast, a complex scenario unfolded as negative effects manifested in relation to credit extended to the public sector and the prime lending rate. This suggests that the impact of credit extends beyond mere availability, emphasizing the critical significance of strategic and targeted allocations. The study underscores the need for a nuanced understanding of credit dynamics, recognizing the diverse implications of its distribution across different sectors of the economy.

Ozili, Oladipo, and Iorember (2023) examined the effect of abnormal increase in credit supply on economic growth in Nigeria after controlling for the quality of the legal system, size of central bank asset, banking sector cost efficiency and bank insolvency risk. The authors employed the generalised method of moments (GMM) regression methodology to estimate the effect of abnormal increase in credit supply on two measures of economic growth in Nigeria. In their findings, the abnormal increase in credit supply has a significant effect on economic growth. Abnormal increase in credit supply

increases real gross domestic product (GDP) growth. The abnormal increase in credit supply decreases real GDP per capita during the global financial crisis. The abnormal increase in domestic credit to the private sector has a significant positive effect on GDP per capita when there is strong legal system quality in Nigeria. In contrast, the abnormal increase in domestic credit to the private sector has a significant negative effect on real GDP growth when there is strong legal system quality in Nigeria.

Idachaba, Olukotun and Elam (2019) studied the Influence of Bank Credits on the Nigerian Economy. The aim of the study was to examine the influence of bank credits on the Nigerian economy using time series data covering the period from 1980 to 2017. Gross domestic product was used as proxy for the economy while credits to the private sector, public sector and prime lending rate were used as proxies of Banks credits. Unit root test was used to test stationary which reveals that all the variables were stationary at first difference. The regression analysis result shows that credit to the private sector have positive effect on Nigerian economy while credit to public sector and prime lending rate have negative effect on the Nigerian economy. The result of co-integration test presented reveals that there exist among the variables co-integration which means long-run analysis. It is recommended that, policy makers should focus attention on long-run policies to promote economic growth such as development of modern banking sector, efficient financial market, infrastructures.

Atseye, Edim and Ezeaku (2015) highlight that despite the fact that credit influences the economy there still remains a gap in understanding the causal relationship between commercial bank credit and its impact in developing economies. The influence of such types of credit on economic growth has received little attention from researchers. Admitting the existence of such gap, Tuuli (2002) states that of course there have been a few empirical findings on the determinants of growth in developing economies, but the relationship between bank credit and the economy has however been neglected.

Modebe, Ugwuegbe and Ugwuoke (2014) investigated the impact of bank credit on the growth of Nigerian economy for the period of 1986-2012; the result of the OLS regression showed that there is a negative and significant relationship between GDP and TBCPS in the long run. M2 which was used as control variable has a positive and significant impact on GDP at the long run. The short run dynamics of the variables indicates that TBCPS also have a negative and insignificant impact on GDP at the short-run. The result of the granger causality test reveals that causation runs from GDP to TBCPS and not the other way round, a case of unidirectional causality. The result also showed bidirectional causality between TBCPS and M2.

Evaluating the relationship between financial development and economic growth, Eatza and Malik

(2009) found that bank credits to the private sector significantly increase the productivity of workers (output per worker) and as such, facilitates long-run economic growth with respect to Nigeria.

In the same way, study by Aliero, Abdullahi and Adamu (2013) over the period 1974-2010 examined the impact of bank credit on economic growth. The result from Autoregressive distributed lag bound approach showed that private sector had significant positive effect on economic growth in Nigeria. Kiran, Yavus and Guris (2009) apply ratios of bank credits to the GDP and private sector credit to the GDP and found a positive and statistically significant relationship between bank credits and economic growth. Murty, Sailaya and Demissie (2012) by using multivariate Johansen co-integration approach examined the long run impact of the bank credit on economic growth of Ethiopia. The study found a significant long-run relationship between bank credits and economic growth in Ethiopia.

Nuno (2012) applied a dynamic panel data (GMM-System Estimator) technique to evaluate the nexus between bank credits and economic growth in the European Union. The study found that savings promotes growth while inflation and bank credits negatively impacted on economic growth. Akpansung and Babalola (2011) found significant long-run relationship between private sector bank credits and economic growth in Nigeria. The causality runs from GDP to private sector bank credits and also from industrial production to GDP, lending rate are found to impede economic growth. Hassan, Sanchez and Yu (2011) assert that rapid bank credit expansion negatively impacts on economic growth. The studies argued that rapid and uncontrolled expansion in bank credits has the tendency to discourage domestic savings and investments. Mulhsin and Eric (2000) carried out a study on Turkish economy; it was found that bank deposits, private sector credit or domestic credit ratios are alternatively used as proxies for financial development; causality runs from economic growth to financial development. Their conclusion was that growth seems to lead financial sector development.

Shittu (2012) adopted unit root test, co-integration and error correction model to examine the impact of financial intermediation on economic growth in Nigeria, the study concludes that credit through deposit is a determinant of economic growth in Nigeria. This is in agreement with the study of Yakubu and Affoi (2014) which conclude that commercial banks credit impacts positively and significantly on the economic growth of Nigeria. Ogege and Boloupremo (2014) employ ADF, Johansen co-integration and ECM, the study concluded that only credit allocated to production sector is having a significant positive effect on growth. Akpansung and Babalola (2009), examined the impact of bank credit on the growth of Nigerian economy for the period of 1970 – 2008, using two-stage least square and granger causality test, the

result indicates that bank credit has a negative impact on the growth of Nigerian economy with causation running from GDP to bank credit.

Marshal, Igbaniho and Onuegbu (2015) did study in Nigeria and found strong positive correlation between banks credit and GDP and concluded that there is unidirectional relationship running from GDP to banking sector credit. Orji, A. (2012) investigated the determinants of bank savings in Nigeria as well as examined the impact of bank savings and bank credits on Nigeria's economic growth from 1970 – 2006. The empirical results showed a positive relationship exists between the lagged values of total private savings, private sector credit, public sector credit, interest rate spread, exchange rates and economic growth.

Yerima and Idris (2023) examined the impact of bank credits on economic growth in Nigeria. The study utilized time series data covering the period of 1986 to 2022. The data were sourced from the annual statistical bulletin of the Central Bank of Nigeria. To analysed the data collected, Johansen cointegration technique and Vector Error Correction Model (VEM) are adopted to measure the long-run and short-run relationship among the study variables. Furthermore, Granger Causality is utilized to measure the direction of causality between banks credits and economic growth. From the analysis, results show that credits to the private sector, credits to the public sector and combined credits to both sectors exacted a positive and significant impact on economic growth. Therefore, this study concludes that for the Nigerian economy to grow, emphasis should be placed on developing and implementing policies that will address increase in banks credit to critical areas like research and education, manufacturing, agriculture, power, infrastructural development etc., as these are growth-oriented areas that can move the country forward.

Mishra (2019) examined the direction of causality that runs between credit market development and the economic growth in India for the period 1980 to 2008. In the VAR framework the application of Granger Causality Test provided the evidence in support of the fact that credit market development spurs economic growth. The empirical investigation indicated a positive effect of economic growth on credit market development of the country.

Mukhopadhyay and Pradhan (2018) recently examined the causal relationship between financial development and economic growth of 7 Asian developing countries (Thailand, Indonesia, Malaysia, the Philippines, China, India and Singapore) during the last 30 years, using multivariate VAR model. The study concluded that no general consensus can be made about the finance-growth relationship in the context of developing countries. Examining the Nigerian experience, Fadare (2018) empirically identifies the effect of banking sector reforms on economic growth in Nigeria by using the data 1999 –

2009. Variables used for the study are interest rate margins, parallel market premiums, total banking sector credit to the private sector, inflation rate, inflation rate lagged by one year, size of banking sector capital and cash reserve ratios. Results indicate that the relationship between economic growth and other exogenous variables of interest rate margins, parallel market premiums, total banking sector credit to the private sector, inflation rate and cash reserve ratio show the negative and insignificant.

Kayode (2020) investigated the effect of bank lending and economic growth on the manufacturing output in Nigeria. Using the times series data which covered a period of 36 years (1973 to 2009), the technique he used for analysis of the model is the co-integration and vector error correction model (VECM) techniques. The empirical outcomes of the study show that production volume utilize in manufacturing and bank rate of lending loans significantly affect manufacturing output in Nigeria. However, at the other hand relationship between manufacturing output and economic growth was found to be significant resulting to a success and progress in the country.

Abdullahi and Adamu (2018) adopted Autoregressive Distributed Lag Bound Approach (ARDL) to examine the relationship between banks' private sector credits and economic growth in Nigeria for the period of 37 years (i.e., 1974 – 2010). The study discovered that significant long-run relationship exists between private sector credits and economic growth, but no significant causality between them in either or both directions. Therefore, the study concluded that Nigerian banks are playing neither supply-leading nor demand-following roles but conform to the Schumpeterian independent hypothesis stage. It was recommended that implementation and adoption of more long-term loans for entrepreneurship ventures in Nigeria should be put in place instead of short term and self-liquidating credit facilities preferred by Nigerian banks.

In the study of Tomola, Adebisi and Olawale (2019) on the effect of bank lending on the growth of manufacturing output in Nigeria. Times series data for the period of 36 years was employed and tested with the co-integration and vector error correction model (VECM) techniques. The study revealed that manufacturing capacity utilization and bank lending rates significantly affect manufacturing output in Nigeria. They suggested that concerted effort by the government, manufacturers and the lending institutions are needed to review the lending and growth policies and provide appropriate macroeconomic environment, in order to encourage investment, lending and borrowing by the financial institutions.

Ajadua (2023) set out to empirically evaluate the impact of deposit money banks' credit on the performance of Nigerian economic growth. Data covering 1986 to 2020 were collected from secondary sources and unit root test, cointegration test and the ECM method used in analyzing

the data. Findings from the study revealed that total bank credit and money supply both had a positive significant relationship with economic growth. Private sector credit had a positive but not significant relationship with economic growth while lending rate had a negative and significant relationship with economic growth. The study thus recommends that the monetary authorities should implement policies favorable to deposit money banks' credit creation and intensify efforts to attract credit to the private sector in order to stimulate economic growth while policies to support the growth of the financial market and banking industry should be enacted and implemented.

Aliakhue and Chukwudi (2020) investigated the influence of Deposit Money banks on the Nigerian economy from 2009 -2018. Employing the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) technique to ascertain the relationship between gross domestic product and the explanatory variables, their findings revealed that the Deposit Money Bank's credit has a significant influence on Nigeria's economy within the period under study. Shittu (2012) employed the unit root test, co-integration test, and error correction model to analyze the effects of financial intermediation on economic growth in Nigeria between 1970 and 2010. The study discovered that a key factor in influencing economic growth in Nigeria is financial intermediation, particularly deposit mobilization. Olokoyo, Taiwo and Akinjare (2016) utilized ANOVA, one sample test, and simple percentage to examine how deposit money bank activity affected Nigerian economic development. Their findings demonstrated that the activities of deposit money banks have a considerable impact on Nigeria's economic development. Using a two-stage least squares method and covering the period 1970 to 2008, Akpansung and Babalola (2012) investigated the relationship between banking sector credit and economic growth in Nigeria. Their findings showed that while lending rates hindered economic growth, private sector credit had a positive impact.

Orji (2012) investigated the determinants of bank savings in Nigeria as well as examined the impact of bank savings and bank credits on Nigeria's economic growth from 1970-2006. The study adopted two impact models; Distributed Lag-Error Correction Model (DL-ECM) and Distributed Model. The empirical results showed a positive influence of values of GDP per capita (PCY), Financial Deepening (FSD), Interest Rate Spread (IRS) and negative influence of Real Interest Rate (RIR) and Inflation Rate (INFR) on the size of private domestic savings. Also, a positive relationship exists between the lagged values of total private savings, private sector credit, public sector credit, interest rate spread, exchange rates and economic growth. We therefore recommend, among others, that government's effort should be geared towards improving per capita income by reducing the unemployment rate in the country in a bid to accelerate growth through enhanced savings.

Onuorah and Ozurumba (2013) explored the necessity of bank credit and economic growth of Nigeria, the paper examines the relationship between bank credit and economic growth in Nigeria over the period under review.

However, the problem associated with bank credit facility is the constraint and regulation imposed by CBN on the percentage of credit to be given to the entrepreneurs. The study used Secondary data from banks credit on sectorial distribution such as production, General commerce, services and others were spread across the period 1980- 2011. Various statistical technique such as Diagnostic test, Unit root, co-integration Var model and Causality test are statistically used to test the stability function, stationary properties, variable relationship and causality effect of the variable and the result revealed that the time series properties of the variables are stationary and co integrated at most 1 with at least 2 co integrating equation. The study also showed that all the bank credit measures such as Total Production Bank Credits (TPTBKC), Total General Commerce Bank Credits (TGCBKC), Total Services Bank Credit (TSCBKC), and Other Banks Credit (OTHBKC) did not granger cause GDP instead GDP exerted influencing factor on them. More so, short run relationship existed between bank credit measures and GDP as sustainable key player in the economy It therefore recommended total supervision and over haul of the banks' credit activities towards encouraging Investors in Nigeria for economic growth.

Anyanwu, Ananwude and Okoye (2017) empirically assessed the impact of commercial banks' lending on economic development of Nigeria from 1986 to 2015 by specifically ascertaining the impact of commercial banks' lending on real gross domestic product and index of industrial production. The data sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin were diagnosed for serial correlation, heteroskedasticity and Ramsey Reset model fitness specification and stationarity. The Johansen co-integration envisaged a long run relationship between commercial banks' lending and gross domestic product but such could be said for index of industrial production. The granger impact assessment result shows that commercial banks' lending has significant impact on real gross domestic product and real gross domestic product on the other hand, has significant impact on credit to private sector. Index of industrial production was not significantly influenced by commercial banks' lending activities. The vector error correction model depicts that for achievement of long-term growth and development of the Nigerian economy, commercial banks' lending is very pivotal as the high interest rate charged by commercial banks' remain a threat to the positive influence of banks' credit to the economy.

Ayeomoni and Aladejana (2016) examined the relationship between agricultural credit and economic growth in Nigeria. The study employed time series data

from Central Bank of Nigeria, Statistical Bulletin and National Bureau of Statistics which spanned from 1986-2014. The study used the methodology of Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL). The findings showed that short and long run relationship existed between agricultural credit and economic growth in both short and long run respectively. Moreover, real exchange rate and private domestic investment as control variables had direct effect on economic growth whereas inflation rate revealed an inverse relationship in the model.

Yakubu and Affoi (2014) determined the impact of the commercial banks credit on economic growth in Nigeria from 1992 to 2012. In order to examine the role of commercial bank credit to the economy, the commercial bank credit to the private sector of the economy was used to estimate its impact on Nigeria's economic growth, which is proxy by gross domestic product. Using the ordinary least square it was found that the commercial bank credit has significant effect on the economic growth in Nigerian.

Atseye, Edim and Ezeaku (2015) analysed the impact of bank credit on economic growth in Nigeria during the period spanning from 1987 to 2012. The study adopted the ex-post facto research design and time series data were collated from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. OLS regression statistic and Granger Causality Test were used to analyse the data. The estimated regression results indicated that bank credit has impacted positively and significantly on economic growth over the period of the study. The study concluded that for continuous growth of the Nigerian economy, policy frameworks that favour more credit allocation to the private sector with minimal interest rate should be encouraged.

Uzomba et al. (2014) investigated the impact and the determinants of deposit money banks' loans and advances granted to agricultural sector in Nigerian sector from 1980 to 2011. In doing this the study employed rigorous econometric methods such as the multiple OLS regression, Philips Perron, unit root stationarity test, Johansen co-integration, parsimonious error correction mechanism and granger causality Test. The results of the study revealed that the overall model is statistically significant and concluded that deposit money banks' loans and advances did make positive impact on the agricultural sector of Nigerian within the period of review.

Oluitan (2013) studied the significance of real bank credit in stimulating real output growth in the case of Nigeria. The study observes that credit granger causes output. In testing the factors that mobilise credit, it finds that exports in general are negatively related to credit. However, while oil exports are negatively related to credit, non-oil export has positive relationship with credit. Credit is also positively linked to capital inflows and imports. These findings suggest that bank credit is inextricably linked to the opening of the economy to

inextricably linked to the opening of the economy to international trade and capital flows in non-oil.

Mohanty, Kumar and Patra (2017) investigated the causal nexus between total credit and growth across the subnational level in India and also examining the effect of credit on economic growth. Kao's residual based cointegration test confirmed the long run association between bank credit and economic growth in 21 states of India for the period 2001-2014. The Dimetriu Herlin panel causality test revealed a bidirectional relationship bank credit and economic growth. The results of the present study revealed that bank credit, capital outlay and developmental expenditure have favourable effect on economic growth of the states.

Ogunmuyiwa et al. (2017) examined the impact of bank credit on growth of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. Time series data from the return to democratic rule in 1999 to 2014 were fitted into the regression model using econometric techniques particularly the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model. Empirical findings showed that bank credit to the private sector has a positive impact on the manufacturing sector. Albeit, a significant impact was found between bank credit and manufacturing growth, the policy implication of this finding is that bank credits drive manufacturing output in Nigeria.

Iwedi, Igbaniho and Onuegbu O. (2014) ascertained the impact of bank domestic credits on the economic growth of Nigeria. Using time series Nigerian data for the period of thirty-three (33) years (1980-2013), credit to private sector, credit to government sector and contingent liability were used as proxy for bank domestic credit while gross domestic product represents economic growth. The augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test results indicated that the data series achieved stationarity after first differencing at the order 1(1). The relative statistics of the estimated model shows that credit to the private sector and credit to the government sector positively and significantly correlate with GDP in the short run. The analysis revealed the existence of poor long run relationship between bank domestic credit indicators and gross domestic product in Nigeria.

Akujuobi and Nwezeaku (2015) evaluated the effect of bank lending activities on economic development in Nigeria, covering the period, 1980-2013. In models 1 and 2, human development index and the industrial gross domestic product, were employed as proxies for human development and industrial development respectively, while commercial bank credit to the general commerce, production, services and other sectors formed components of bank lending activities. Applying the test for stationarity with the Ordinary Least Square (OLS), and cointegration procedures, the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between bank lending activities and economic development was tested. The results revealed a significant relationship between bank lending

activities and economic development in Nigeria. Whereas in model 1, both credit to the general commerce and production sectors were statistically significant as well as met the a priori expectation, model 2 showed that only credit to the services sector carried the wrong sign and at the same time was statistically insignificant.

Adenugba (2015) determined banking system credit as an instrument of economic growth in Nigeria. The purpose of carrying this research work was to identify the reasons why bank lending or access to credit to the poor and Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SME) has remained low, to examine the reasons why banking habit is low in Nigeria and to identify the factors or criteria that ensures diligent and prudent credit approval. Time series data collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin between periods of (1983-2012) was used to regress the model using the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) technique. Findings showed that banking system credit is indeed an instrument of economic growth in Nigeria.

Nwaru and Okorontah (2014) studied the significance of banks credit in stimulating output and the factors that prompt financial intermediation within the economy. Evidence from the study showed that the marginal productivity coefficient of bank credit to the domestic economy (proxies by credit to the private sector) is positive but insignificant. The implication is that banks' credit did not affect the productive sectors sufficiently for the later to impact significantly on the Nigerian economy. It was also observed that real output causes financial development, but not vice versa, and that export was not significant in driving financial development; but growth in financial sector was highly dependent on foreign capital inflows.

Ehikioya and Mohammed (2013) analysed the impact of commercial bank credit accessibility and sectoral output performance in Nigerian economy for the period which spanned between 1986 and 2010. An augmented growth model was estimated via the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) techniques to ascertain the relationship between various commercial bank credits and sectoral output growth. The variables were tested for stationarity and co-integration analysis was also carried out using the Augmented Dickey Fuller test. Also, error correction test was performed. The study found that the various commercial bank credit supply and other included variables has a long run relationship with sectoral output performance i.e. agricultural, manufacturing and services sector output and the main demand for credit facility in Nigeria is the manufacturing sector. The study also reveal that commercial bank credit has direct and insignificant impact on sectoral output performance but cumulative supply and demand for credit in the previous period has direct and significant impact on the growth of agriculture, manufacturing and the services sectors output.

Olusegun, Akintoye and Dada (2014) reviewed the

impact of commercial bank lending on Nigeria's aggregate economic growth for the period 1970-2011. The research work borrowed from the theoretical underpinning of the role of commercial bank lending in economic growth based on the combination of the quantity theory of money and aggregate production function. A regression analysis was undertaken with a model that related the non-oil GDP as dependent variable to commercial bank credit for current and one-year lagged period as the independent variables. The linear regression model showed that the previous year's loans and advances to services sector had more positive impact on economic growth compared with the current year's loans and advances. The results show that both previous and current year's credit to 'others' sector had inverse relationship with economic growth. In terms of the subsectors, the previous year's credit to public utilities and transport/telecommunications sub-sectors showed positive contributions to economic growth while the impact of that of current year was negative.

Ojeaga, Odejimi, Okhiku and Ojeaga (2018) ascertained the effect of bank lending on growth in Nigeria using a sample of data from 1989 to 2012 (23 years). The method of estimation used in the study is the quantile regression estimation method. It was found that commercial bank lending was having a negative effect on growth while institutions were not sufficiently protecting customers from the negative effect that often arise when banks liquidate. Central bank policies were found to be minimizing bank losses and helping to drive economic growth in general.

Emecheta and Ibe (2014) determined the impact of bank credit on economic growth in Nigeria applying the reduced form of vector autoregressive (VAR) technique using time series data from 1960 to 2011. Current gross domestic product (GDP) is the dependent variable and proxy for economic growth while bank credit to the private sector (CPS) to GDP ratio and broad money (M2) to GDP ratio were proxies for financial indicator and financial depth respectively. They tested the stationarity of the variables using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips Perron (PP) unit root tests. All the variables were integrated of order one i.e., $I(1)$. A major finding is that there is a significant positive relationship between bank credit to the private sector, broad money and economic growth. The past values of all the variables were significant in predicting their current values.

Oni, Akinlo and Oladepo (2014), studied the impact of bank credit to output growth in the manufacturing and agricultural sub sectors of the economy over the period 1980 – 2010. Using the error correction modelling techniques, the results showed that bank credit has significant impact on manufacturing output growth both in the short run and long run but not in the agricultural sub sector. Inflation and exchange rate depreciation have negative effects on manufacturing output growth in both

short run and long run.

Olowofeso et al. (2017) investigated the impacts of private sector credit on economic growth in Nigeria using the Gregory and Hansen (1996) co-integration test that accounted for structural breaks and endogeneity problems. The method was applied to quarterly data spanning 2000: Q1 to 2014: Q4, while the fully modified ordinary least squares procedure was employed to estimate the model coefficients. We found a co-integrating relationship between output and its selected determinants, albeit, with a structural break in 2012: Q1. Amongst others, findings from the error correction model confirmed a positive and statistically significant effect of private sector credit on output, while increased prime lending rate was inhibiting growth.

Mamman and Hashim (2018) analysed the impact of credit to private sector (CPS) on the real sector of Nigeria with a view to assess the significant contribution of CPS to real sector growth in Nigeria. The study used aggregate time series data from 1986 to 2010, which was drawn from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin and the CBN Annual Report and Statement of Accounts. The data was analysed using multiple regression and based on the coefficient of determination (R-square). The study reveals a 96.1% variation between the CPS and real sector growth in Nigeria. The study concluded that there is a statistically significant impact of credit to private sector on the real sector of Nigeria.

Makinde (2017) explored the implications of commercial bank loans on economic growth in Nigeria between 1986 and 2014. The study made use of secondary data sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and the National Bureau of Statistics between 1986 and 2014. The model for the study has as its dependent variable the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and its explanatory variables were commercial bank loans to key sectors like industrial, manufacturing, agriculture and the service sectors. Using the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) multiple regression techniques; the study revealed that only the agricultural sector have been enjoying much of the bank's credit and it has been making positive impact on the Gross Domestic products (GDP) while others like Mining and Quarrying, Manufacturing and the Building and Constructions sectors have not been getting much attention in terms of bank credit to spur development in that sector.

Balago (2014) looked into the relationship between bank credit and economic growth in Nigeria by considering the total bank credit extended to the production sector which comprises manufacturing, agriculture, fishery and forestry, mining and quarrying, real estate and construction, general commerce sector comprising bills discounted, domestic trade, exports and imports; and services sector comprising public utilities, transport and communication, credit to financial institutions. Time series data from 1983 – 2012 were

fitted into the regression equation using various econometric techniques such as stationarity test using Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) and Johansen Multivariate Co-Integration Test. The Ordinary Least Square Regression (OLS) and VEC Models were used to analyze the relationship between the independent variables (total credits to production, general commerce and services sectors) and dependent variable (real gross domestic product). The result of the OLS showed that total bank credit to production, general commerce and services sectors has a positive relationship with the gross domestic product. Similarly, the VEC model result shows that causality runs from bank credit to the GDP.

Okafor, Ezeaku, and Ugwuegbe (2016) evaluated the causal relationship between deposit money bank credit and economic growth in Nigeria over the period 1981 – 2014. The technique of analysis employed was the Vector Autoregressive (VAR) Granger causality test. The proxied variables, real gross domestic product (RGDP), private sector credit (PSC) and broad money supply (M2) were subjected to preliminary tests while a validity test of serial autocorrelation was also conducted on the residuals of the variables. The results revealed a unidirectional causality running from private sector credit and broad money supply to economic growth as measured by real gross domestic product (RGDP), whereas there was no feedback system from RGDP to either PSC or M2. In other words, RGDP was neither Granger causal for PSC nor M2. This result confirms the significance of financial development to economic growth. Banking system credit is therefore critical for the growth of the economy.

Bakare, Akano and Kazeem (2015) examined the extent to which banks' credit affects economic growth in Nigeria. The data used was collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin for a period of 24 years from 1990 to 2013. We used credit to the private sector, credit to the public sector and inflation to proxy commercial bank credit while Gross Domestic Product proxies' economic growth. Augmented Dickey Fuller (unit root) test was used to test stationarity which reveals that all the independent variables and dependent variable were stationary at first difference, the trace statistics and maximum eigen value test were used to test for co-integration. The result shows that the lagged value of credit to the private sector is positively and significantly influencing economic growth in Nigeria while the lagged value of credit to the public sector shows a positively insignificant relationship with GDP. Lagged value of inflation shows a negatively significant relationship with economic growth.

Ubesie, Echekoba, Chris-Ejiogu, and Ananwude (2019) explored the effect of sectoral allocation of deposit money banks' credit on the growth of the Nigerian real economy from 2008: Q1 to 2017: Q4 was evaluated. The authors were inspired by the unsettled disparity in empirical

literature on the effect of sectoral allocation of deposit money banks credit on the growth of the real economy. Specifically, they ascertained the effect of deposit money banks' sectoral credit on agricultural, industrial, building & construction and wholesale & retail trade contribution to real gross domestic product. The result of the analysis revealed that deposit money banks' credit to agriculture, industries, building & construction and wholesale & retail trade have no significant effect on agricultural, industrial, building & construction and wholesale & retail trade contribution to real gross domestic product.

Finally, Nwonye, Anowor, Uzomba, Abu, Chikwendu, Ojiogu, and Edeh (2020) adopting Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag bounds testing approach reflected on financial intermediation in an attempt to assess how it has affected economic performance (proxied by output per capita). The empirical results denoted that funds to the private sector are trapped in the incessant risks prevalent in developing economies; the implication is that any increase in per capita output could have emanated from seldom-productive sources like sales of natural resources that rarely have intersectoral links. The study thus recommends that there should be a consistent fight from the demand and supply side plus political approach to ensure adequate monitoring.

Gap in Literature

The empirical link between financial intermediation and economic growth has long been a subject of intense scrutiny. However, it is too hasty to uphold any of the views either for financial intermediation spurring economic growth or against as even shown in the theoretical foundation.

For this study, the major concern is that whatever change resulted from financial intermediation should be reflected in the economic performance of the said economy. In other words, the citizenry should be better off tangibly as a result of the gain from financial intermediation. It would seem that there are yet to be studies that had examined how financial intermediation affects output per capita (as a proxy for economic performance) as well as the direction of casualty between them. Given these concerns, this study therefore is an attempt to explore the empirical nature of the linkage between financial intermediation and economic performance in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Following the previous work of Nwonye et al. (2020), the study utilizes the Johansen's Co-integration and Error Correction Model for both long run and short run analyses. However, it must be stated that this study is an improvement in the work of the authors, especially in

terms of variables of study; as Nwoye et al. (2020) seemed to neglect the savings mobilization side of financial intermediation.

Data

The data for this study – Gross Domestic Product Per Capita (GDPPC), Deposit Rate (DEPR), Lending Rate (LDNR), Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), Savings Mobilization (SAV) and Credit Extension (CRE) from 1981 – 2022 were collected as published from the Central Bank of Nigeria's Statistical Bulletin and World Bank Data Publication covering the period 1981 – 2022 as presented in table 1 below.

Transformation of Data

To ensure that the normality distribution property is achieved and also for a better result for analysis, the study data are made to have the same order of magnitude. This is achieved by transforming all the data variables into their natural logarithm form.

Specification of Tools for Analyses and Tests

The following tests are carried out to ensure that the key objectives are achieved – Stationarity (Unit root) Test, Co-integration Test, Error Correction Estimates and Causality Tests. This subsection is further subdivided as follows:

Test for Stationarity (Unit Root Test)

This study investigates the stationarity of the time-series variables. Non stationarity of the time series data could lead to spurious estimates. In view of the above, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test was employed in accordance with equation (1) below;

$$\Delta y_t = \alpha + \beta t + \gamma y_{t-1} + \delta_1 \Delta y_{t-1} + \dots + \delta_{p-1} \Delta y_{t-p+1} + \varepsilon_t, \dots \quad 1$$

Where;

α = constant,

β = the coefficient on a time trend

P = the lag order of the autoregressive process

Y = variable of choice

Δ = first difference operator

For the ADF test, the null hypothesis is $y = 0$ and the alternative hypothesis is $y < 0$. Rejection of the null hypothesis is an indication that the series y is stationary.

Co-integration Tests

Co-integration tests are carried out in order to ascertain

Table 1: Gross Domestic Product Per Capita (GDPPC), Deposit Rate (DEPR), Lending Rate (LDNR), Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), Savings Mobilization (SAV) and Credit Extension (CRE) from 1981 – 2022.

Year	GDP Per Capita (\$)	Deposit Rate (%)	Lending Rate (%)	Monetary Policy Rate (%)	Savings Mobilization (N'B)	Credit Extension ((N'B))
1981	2187.886436	6.00	7.75	6.00	6.56	12.56
1982	1844.849844	7.50	10.25	8.00	7.51	15.51
1983	1223.603921	7.50	10.00	8.00	9.44	17.44
1984	903.4493516	9.50	12.50	10.00	10.99	20.99
1985	882.2827027	9.50	9.25	10.00	12.52	22.52
1986	638.7316957	9.50	10.50	10.00	13.93	23.93
1987	598.2909687	14.00	17.50	12.75	18.68	31.43
1988	549.5037556	14.50	16.50	12.75	23.25	36.00
1989	474.4569001	16.40	26.80	18.50	23.80	42.30
1990	567.5179022	18.80	25.50	18.50	29.65	48.15
1991	609.3731283	14.29	20.01	15.50	37.74	53.24
1992	519.6358475	16.10	29.80	17.50	55.12	72.62
1993	551.8929192	16.66	18.32	26.00	85.03	111.03
1994	762.3987332	13.50	21.00	13.50	110.97	124.47
1995	1302.550052	12.61	20.18	13.50	108.49	121.99
1996	1673.906146	11.69	19.74	13.50	134.50	148.00
1997	1765.078768	4.80	13.54	13.50	177.65	191.15
1998	1871.756057	5.49	18.29	13.50	200.07	213.57
1999	494.1292273	5.33	21.32	18.00	277.67	295.67
2000	563.0470862	5.29	17.98	14.00	385.19	399.19
2001	583.0858388	5.49	18.29	20.50	488.05	508.55
2002	733.5378887	4.15	24.85	16.50	592.09	608.59
2003	786.8022148	4.11	20.71	15.00	655.74	670.74
2004	992.7453991	4.19	19.18	15.00	797.52	812.52
2005	1250.406913	3.83	17.95	13.00	1,316.96	1,329.96
2006	1652.154002	3.14	17.26	10.00	1,739.64	1,749.64
2007	1876.413033	3.55	16.94	9.50	2,686.84	2,696.34
2008	2227.790349	2.84	15.14	9.75	4,247.83	4,257.58
2009	1883.887783	2.68	18.99	6.00	5,707.99	5,713.99
2010	2280.111289	2.21	17.59	6.25	5,941.37	5,947.62
2011	2504.879101	1.41	16.02	12.00	6,526.69	6,538.69
2012	2728.022788	1.70	16.79	12.00	8,021.19	8,033.19
2013	2976.756832	2.17	16.72	12.00	9,603.45	9,615.45
2014	3200.952799	3.38	16.55	13.00	11,451.59	11,464.59
2015	2679.554223	3.58	16.85	11.00	11,763.92	11,774.92
2016	2144.780344	3.75	16.87	14.00	14,034.23	14,048.23
2017	1941.879479	4.13	17.56	14.00	14,464.64	14,478.64
2018	2125.834491	4.07	19.33	14.00	14,559.43	14,573.43
2019	2334.023642	3.95	15.53	13.50	16,893.19	16,906.69
2020	2074.613748	3.22	12.32	11.50	20,841.84	20,853.34
2021	2065.77441	1.69	11.48	11.50	25,589.29	25,600.79
2022	2162.633732	2.34	12.34	16.50	30,240.02	30,256.52

Source: Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin 2022 and World Bank Data Publication 2023

the nature of long-run relationship which prevails among the variables of study. This is done through the Johansen's Co-integration test. The decision rule is that the 'Trace Statistic' is greater than the 'Critical Value'.

Error Correction Estimates

It is theoretically expected that some deviations from long

run relationship could occur due to distortions in any of the variables in the short run. Consequently, an Error Correction Model (ECM) is employed to adjust for these short-run dynamics.

Test for Causality

The test for causality or feedback effects between the

Table 2: Results of ADF (Unit Root) Tests:

Variables	ADF t-statistics	Critical value			Order	Probability
		1%	5%	10%		
LOG(GDPPC)	-4.292176	-3.600987	-2.935001	-2.605836	I(1)	0.0031
LOG(MPR)	-3.933783	-3.600987	-2.935001	-2.605836	I(1)	0.0251
LOG(DEPR)	-4.802439	-3.600987	-2.935001	-2.605836	I(1)	0.0078
LOG(LDNR)	-8.833614	-3.605593	-2.936942	-2.606857	I(1)	0.0000
LOG(SAV)	-5.873267	-3.605593	-2.936942	-2.606857	I(1)	0.0004
LOG(CRE)	-5.249090	-3.605593	-2.936942	-2.606857	I(1)	0.0005

Source: Author's Computation using E-views 10 software

Table 3: Results of Johansen's Co-integration Tests

Date: 09/25/24 Time: 14:29				
Sample (adjusted): 1983 2022				
Included observations: 40 after adjustments				
Trend assumption: Linear deterministic trend				
Series: LOG(GDPPC) LOG(MPR) LOG(DEPR) LOG(LDNR) LOG(SAV) LOG(CRE)				
Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 1				
Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)				
Hypothesized		Trace	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.564290	102.2839	95.75366	0.0065
At most 1	0.522541	79.05279	69.81889	0.0074
At most 2	0.359310	59.48167	47.85613	0.0416
At most 3	0.230822	21.67331	29.79707	0.3170
At most 4	0.155714	11.17600	15.49471	0.2009
At most 5 *	0.104288	4.405464	3.841466	0.0358
Trace test indicates 3 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level				
* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level				
**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values				

Source: Author's Computation using E-views 10 software

specified variables was executed through the employment of Granger Causality Technique in order to ascertain the extent to which the study variables do promote and/or support themselves in an economic or financial setting. A time series X is said to Granger-cause Y if in a series of regression equations, the inclusion of lagged values of X improves the explanations for Y and vice versa.

Granger Causality relationships are typified by equations (2) and (3) below;

$$(Y)_t = \alpha + \sum_{i=1}^m \beta_i (Y)_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^m \Gamma_j (X)_{t-j} + U_t \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

$$(X)_t = \Theta + \sum_{i=1}^m \gamma_i (X)_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^m \Upsilon_j (Y)_{t-j} + \epsilon_t \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Where Y_t and X_t are the time series variables under test, while U_t and ϵ_t are serially independent random vectors with zero mean and finite covariance matrix.

Model Specification

This study seeks to ascertain the nature and dimensions of relationship between financial intermediation and economic performance of Nigeria. Gross Domestic Product Per Capita (GDPPC), a proxy for economic performance constitutes the dependent variable, while Deposit Rate (DEPR), Lending Rate (LDNR), Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), Savings Mobilization (SAV) and Credit Extension (CRE) from 1981 – 2022 proxies for financial intermediation process and represent explanatory variables of the study.

The econometric form of the model is stated as:

$$GDPPC = f (DEPR, LDNR, MPR, SAV, CRE) \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Table 4: Results of the Error Correction Model (ECM)

Dependent Variable: D(LOG(GDPPC))				
Method: Least Squares				
Date: 09/25/24 Time: 16:13				
Sample (adjusted): 1984 2022				
Included observations: 39 after adjustments				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.78E-17	1.69E-17	1.051299	0.3012
D(LOG(GDPPC(-1)))	1.000000	3.34E-17	3.00E+16	0.0000
D(LOG(MPR))	-9.44E-17	4.24E-17	-2.224875	0.0535
D(LOG(DEPR))	0.766707	2.362394	-0.324547	0.0085
D(LOG(LDNR))	49.70636	1350.061	-0.036818	0.0859
D(LOG(SAV))	4.88E-16	2.14E-16	-2.274285	0.0300
D(LOG(CRE))	-0.321916	2.18E-16	2.059110	0.0480
ECM(-1)	-0.783326	0.136386	-1.344174	0.0020
R-squared	0.590817	Mean dependent var	5.33E+08	
Adjusted R-squared	0.556718	S.D. dependent var	1.84E+09	
S.E. of regression	1.84E+09	Akaike info criterion	45.61099	
Sum squared resid	7.78E+19	Schwarz criterion	45.75616	
Log likelihood	-589.9429	Hannan-Quinn criter.	45.65280	
F-statistic	17.32673	Durbin-Watson stat	1.577742	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000022			

Source: Author's Computation using E-views 10 software

Where;

GDPPC = Gross Domestic Product Per Capita

DEPR = Deposit Rate

LDNR = Lending Rate

MPR = Monetary Policy Rate

SAV = Savings Mobilization

CRE = Credit Extension

For estimation purposes, equation (1) is further restated as follows;

$$GDPPC_t = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 DEPR_t + \beta_2 LDNR_t + \beta_3 MPR_t + \beta_4 SAV_t + \beta_5 CRE_t + \varepsilon_t \text{----- (2)}$$

Where;

α_0 represents the constant term. ε_t is a white noise disturbance term and $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$, are parameters to be estimated.

PRESENTATION OF EMPIRICAL RESULTS

Stationarity Tests

The result of stationarity (unit root) test is shown in the table 2 below;

The Unit root (ADF) results presented in table 2 above show that for all the variables (Gross Domestic Product Per Capita (GDPPC), Deposit Rate (DEPR), Lending Rate (LDNR), Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), Savings

Mobilization (SAV) and Credit Extension (CRE)) in their natural logarithm forms, the absolute values of the ADF Test Statistics for all the study variables are relatively higher than all the associated critical values at various levels of significance (1%, 5% and 10%). Further, the variables are stationary at first difference and are consequently said to be integrated of order 1; i.e., I (1). Their associated probability values show that they are all significant at 0.05 level of significance.

Co-integration Test Results

The results of the Johansen's Co-integration tests are presented in table 3 below;

The results of Johansen's maximum likelihood co-integration above do not indicate any full-rank trend. They show that there are two co-integrating equations. This is strong evidence to suggest that there exists a long-run relationship among the study variables. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no co-integration is rejected.

Presentation of Error Correction Model Estimates

The results of the Error Correction Model are shown in table 4 above; The ECM results shown in table 4 above reveal that the explanatory variables jointly account for

Table 5: Results of Granger causality Tests:

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests			
Date: 09/27/24 Time: 11:49			
Sample: 1981 2022			
Lags: 2			
Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
D(MPR) does not Granger Cause D(GDPPC)	39	0.19738	0.8218
D(GDPPC) does not Granger Cause D(MPR)		2.64211	0.0858
D(LDNR) does not Granger Cause D(GDPPC)	39	0.09258	0.9118
D(GDPPC) does not Granger Cause D(LDNR)		0.52830	0.5944
D(DEPR) does not Granger Cause D(GDPPC)	39	1.78492	0.0032
D(GDPPC) does not Granger Cause D(DEPR)		1.78222	0.1836
D(SAV) does not Granger Cause D(GDPPC)	39	0.10549	0.0002
D(GDPPC) does not Granger Cause D(SAV)		0.74453	0.0025
D(CRE) does not Granger Cause D(GDPPC)	39	0.10615	0.8996
D(GDPPC) does not Granger Cause D(CRE)		0.74267	0.4834

Source: Author's Computation using E-views 10 software

55.6 percent of the changes in gross domestic product per capita (GDPPC) after adjusting for short run distortions as shown by the coefficient of determination (the adjusted R-squared). The Durbin-Watson statistics (1.57) is within the acceptable range. The absolute value of the ECM is 78.3 percent, showing that 78.3 percent of distortion in the long run have been corrected. It is statistically significant at 0.05 level.

Specifically, the results provide evidence that gross domestic product per capita of immediate past period $D(\text{LOG}(\text{GDPPC}(-1)))$, deposit rate $D(\text{LOG}(\text{DEPR}))$, savings mobilization $D(\text{LOG}(\text{SAV}))$ as well as credit extension $D(\text{LOG}(\text{CRE}))$ are all significant in explaining variations in gross domestic product per capita $D(\text{LOG}(\text{GDPPC}))$, the dependent variable. On the other hand, however, monetary policy rate $D(\text{LOG}(\text{MPR}))$ and lending rate $D(\text{LOG}(\text{CRE}))$ show insignificant relationship with the dependent variable, gross domestic product per capita. The probability estimates of the relationship between gross domestic product per capita of immediate past period $D(\text{LOG}(\text{GDPPC}(-1)))$, deposit rate $D(\text{LOG}(\text{DEPR}))$, savings mobilization $D(\text{LOG}(\text{SAV}))$ as well as credit extension $D(\text{LOG}(\text{CRE}))$ and gross domestic product per capita $D(\text{LOG}(\text{GDPPC}))$, the dependent variable are 0.0000, 0.0085, 0.0300 and 0.0480 respectively. These figures are less than 0.05 level of significance showing evidence of significant relationship between each of the predictor variables and the criterion variable. On the other hand, the probability

estimates of the relationship between monetary policy rate $D(\text{LOG}(\text{MPR}))$, lending rate $D(\text{LOG}(\text{CRE}))$ and gross domestic product per capita are 0.0535 and 0.0859 respectively. The probability estimates are greater than our preferred level of significance, (0.05) indicating an insignificant relationship.

Presentation of Granger Causality Tests.

The results of Granger Causality tests are presented below in table 5;

The Granger causality estimation test result on the direction of causality shows that there exists a significant uni-directional relationship between deposit rate and gross domestic product per capita with the direction of causality stemming from deposit rate to gross domestic product per capita. Also. A significant bi-directional causal relationship exists between savings mobilization and gross domestic product per capita.

Discussions, Conclusion and Recommendations

The role of financial intermediation in promoting economic development cannot be overemphasized. This role is even more evident in developing economies like Nigeria where there is dire need to promote and encourage efficient and effective mobilization of savings and allocation of credits for sustainable economic growth and development.

From our findings, credit extension showed a statistically significant impact on gross domestic product per capita even in the current period. However, the relationship is negative. This might be explained by prevailing morale hazard in most developing economy where credits are diverted to avenues that were not originally intended including diverting credits for consumption purpose rather than into productive activities. This finding is in line with that of (Nwoye et al. 2020; Onodugo, Kalu & Anowor, 2013; Okerenta & Orebiyi, 2005), who found that credit to the private sector seems to explain the variation in economic growth. Also, as expected, there is a significant positive relationship between deposit rate and economic development. This shows that when the financial institutions promise higher deposit rate, individual will be willing to lodge in their surplus funds in expectation of high return; and this consequently improve the credit extension of the financial intermediaries resulting in positive financial intermediation (Toby & Dibiah, 2022). Another important finding worth mentioning is the ability of gross domestic product per capita of immediate past period to positively and significantly influence current gross domestic product per capita, signifying an important lead effect of economic development. In other words, there is a compounding effect of improved standard of living on the citizenry.

On the other hand, the results show that monetary policy rate and lending rate are not significant in explaining changes in economic development. This is no surprise as studies in economics and finance literature have consistently shown that in Nigeria, just like most developing counties, interest rates are not potential tools in influencing economic growth. This is because economic agents are largely not sensitive to interest rate movement. These findings are further corroborated by the results of the Granger Causality estimates which showed a significant uni-directional relationship between deposit rate and gross domestic product per capita with the direction of causality stemming from deposit rate to gross domestic product per capita. Also, a significant bi-directional causal relationship exists between savings mobilization and gross domestic product per capita.

In view of the discussions above, one can see a mixed outcome on the effect of financial intermediation on economic development. From the savings mobilization angle, a positive and significant effect is noticed. However, this cannot be said from the credit extension angle where lending rate is not significant in influencing economic development. Also credit extension though positive showed a negative relationship with economic development confirming possible sign of loan diversion. It is concluded that efficient and effective mobilization of savings and allocation of credits is a panacea for sustainable economic growth and development (Toby & Dibiah, 2022; Nwoye et al. 2020; Onodugo, Kalu & Anowor, 2013; Okerenta & Orebiyi, 2005). Consequently, the study therefore recommends that the monetary authority should

Persuade deposit money banks to reduce the current interest rate spread by a commensurate increase in the deposit rates. This would afford individuals especially in the rural areas the willingness to lodge in their surplus funds in expectation of high return; consequently, improving significantly financial inclusion rate as the level of domestic savings would increase.

Also, effective supervision and monitoring of extended credits is strongly recommended. This will guard against prevailing moral hazards and ensuring that loans are not diverted but are truly utilized for productive purposes for which they are originally meant.

REFERENCES

- Abdullahi, S. I., Tsauni, A. M., & Shuaibu, M. (2022). Economic Growth, Banking Sector Liabilities and Private Saving in Nigeria: Do Bank Deposits Matter? *NDIC QUARTERLY*, 37(3).
- Abdullahi, K., Aliero, H. M., Zakari, Y., & Abubakar, M. Y. (2024). Financial literacy and savings behaviour: a study of academic employees in tertiary institutions of Kano State. *International Journal of Advances in Social Science and Humanities*, 01-11.
- Adenugba A. A. (2015) Banking system credit as an instrument of economic growth in Nigeria (1983 - 2012). *European Journal of Business, Economics and Accountancy*. 2015;3(7):1-23.
- Agbarakwe, U. H., Anowor, O., & Ikue, J. (2018). Foreign resources and economic growth in English speaking ECOWAS countries. *Opción: Revista de Ciencias Humanas y Sociales*, (14), 117-136.
- Akpansung A. O. & Babalola S. J. (2012) Banking sector credit and economic growth in Nigeria: An empirical investigation. *CBN Journal of Applied Statistics*. 2011;2(2):51- 62
- Akujuobi A. B. C. & Nwezeaku N. C. (2015) Bank lending activities and economic development in Nigeria: An empirical investigation. *International Proceedings of Economics Development and Research*, Singapore; 2015
- Ajudua, E. I. (2023). Deposit Money Bank Credit and the Nigerian Economic Growth: An Empirical Analysis. *Economic Insights-Trends & Challenges*, (2).
- Alege, P. O., & Ogunrinola, I. O. (2008). Financial sector reforms and growth of the Nigerian economy. *Lagos Journal of Banking, Finance, and Economic Issues*, 2(1), 50-76.
- Alenoghena, R., Enakali-Osoba, C. & Mesagan, E. (2014), Financial deepening and performance of the Nigerian Capital Market: Empirical Evidence, *Global Journal of Commerce and Management Perspective*, 3(4), 142-151
- Allen, D. S., & Ndikumana, L. (2000). Financial intermediation and economic growth in Southern Africa. *Journal of African economies*, 9(2), 132-160.
- Anyanwu, F., Ananwude, A., & Okoye, N. (2017). An Empirical Assessment of the Impact of Commercial Banks' Lending on Economic Development of Nigeria. *International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting*, 1(1), 14-29.
- Ayeomoni, I. O., & Aladejana, S. A. (2016). Agricultural credit and economic growth nexus. Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*, 6(2), 146-158.
- Atseye, F. A., Edim, N. O., & Ezeaku, H. C. (2015). An Empirical Investigation of the Impact of Bank Credit on Economic Growth in Nigeria. *Indian Journal of Applied Research*, 5(11), 268.
- Balago G. S. (2014) Nexus between bank credit and economic growth in Nigeria: Evidence from VEC Model; 2014. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/oalib.1100952>
- Bakare, I. A. O., Akano, A. I., & Kazeem, H. S. (2015). To what extent does banks' credit stimulate economic growth? evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Development*. 2015; 13(1): 128-139.
- Ehikioya I. L., & Mohammed I. (2013) Commercial bank credit

- accessibility and sectoral output performance in a deregulated financial market economy: Empirical evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Finance and Bank Management*. 2013; 1(2): 37-59.
- Ekpenyong B. & Ikechukwu A. (2011): Banks and economic growth in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management*. 1(1), 1-18
- Emecheta B. C., & Ibe R. C. (2014). Impact of bank credit on economic growth in Nigeria: Application of reduced Vector Autoregressive (VAR) technique. *European Journal of Accounting Auditing and Finance Research*. 2014;2(9):11-21.
- Ewetan, O. O., & Okodua, H. (2013). Is There a Link Between Financial Sector Development and Economic Growth in Nigeria? *International Journal of Financial Economics*, 1(4), 108-118.
- Ganiyu, B. A., Amoo, M. I., Eboime, Y. A., & Belonwu, M. C. (2017). The impact of private sector credit on economic growth in Nigeria. *CBN Journal of Applied Statistics*, 8(2), 1-22.
- Gerschenkron, A. (1962). Economic backwardness in historical perspective: a book of essays. Belknap Press of Harvard University Press.
- Hassan, M. K., Sanchez, B., & Yu, J. S. (2011). Financial development and economic growth: New evidence from panel data. *The Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance*, 51(1), 88-104.
- Korkmaz, S. (2015). Impact of bank credits on economic growth and inflation. *Journal of applied finance and banking*, 5(1), 51.
- Idachaba, O. I., Olukotun G. A., & Elam, W. G. (2019). Influence of bank credits on the Nigerian economy. *American Economic & Social Review*, 5(1), 1-9.
- Iwedi M., Igbanibo D. S. and Onuegbu O. (2014). Bank domestic credits and economic growth nexus in Nigeria (1980-2013). *International Journal of Finance and Accounting*. 2015;4(5):236-244.
- Kiran, B., Yavuz, N. C., & Guris, B. (2009). Financial development and economic growth: A panel data analysis of emerging countries. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, 30(2), 87-94.
- Levine, R., Loayza, N., & Beck, T. (2000). Financial intermediation and growth: Causality and causes. *Journal of monetary Economics*, 46(1), 31-77.
- Makinde H.O. (2016). Implications of commercial bank loans on economic growth in Nigeria (1986-2014). *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics and Management Sciences*. 2016; 7(3): 124-136
- Mamman A, & Hashim Y. A. (2018). Impact of private sector credit on the real sector of Nigeria; 2012. Available:www/http:ssrn.com Accessed: 30th June, 2018
- Mahran, H. A. (2012) *Modern economy*, 3(05), 626-640.
- Mckinnon (1973): Money and Capital in Economic Development. Washington, D.C.: Brookings Institution.
- Mgbataogu, I.S. & Nwakanma, P.C. (2013). Influence of interest rates regimes on deposit money banks' credit in Nigeria: An econometric assessment. *International Journal of Empirical Finance*, 1(3), 52-64.
- Mishra, P. K., Das, K. B., & Pradhan, B. B. (2009). Credit market development and economic growth in India. *Middle Eastern Finance and Economics*, 5(3), 92-106.
- Modebe N. J., Ugwuegbe S. U., & Ugwuoke, R. O. (2014) The impact of bank credit on the growth of Nigerian economy: A co integration approach. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*. 2014; 5(10): 87-95
- Mohanty A. R., Kumar S. & Patra S. K. (2017) Bank credit and economic growth: Empirical evidence from Indian states. *International Journal of Current Research*. 2016;8(9): 39145-39151
- Mukhopadhyay, B., & Pradhan, R.P. (2010). An investigation of the finance-growth nexus: Study of Asian developing countries using multivariate VAR model. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, 58, 134-140.
- Murty, K.S., K. Sailaja & W.M. Dimissie (2012). The long-run impact of bank credit on economic growth in Ethiopia: Evidence from the cointegration approach. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 4(14).
- Nnamdi, I. S., & Mgbataogu, I. S. (2015). Bank deposits and demand for credits in Nigeria: What lessons are available? *Journal of Accounting and Finance Management*, 1(8), 11-22.
- Nuno, C. L. (2012). Bank Credit and Economic Growth: A Dynamic Panel Data Analysis, *The Economic Research Guardian*, Vol. 2, No.2, pp. 256-267
- Nwaru, N. M., & Okorontah, C. F. (2014). Banks' credit as an instrument of economic growth in Nigeria. *Int J Bus Law Res*, 5(2), 102-110.
- Nwonye, N. G., Anowor, O. F., Uzomba, P. C., Abu, A., Chikwendu, N. F., Ojiogu, M. C., & Edeh, C. C. (2020). Financial Intermediation and Economic Performance in Nigeria: An ARDL Approach. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(7), 8353-8361.
- Ogunmuyiwa, M. S., Okuneye, B. A., & Amaefule, J. N. (2017). Bank credit and growth of the manufacturing sector nexus in Nigeria: An ARDL approach. *EuroEconomica*, 36(2), 62-72.
- Okafor I. G., Ezeaku H. C., & Ugwuegbe U. S. (2016). Relationship between deposit money bank credit and economic growth in Nigeria under a VAR G-causality environment. *Journal of Economics and Finance*. 2016; 7(2):41-46
- Okerenta, S. I., & Orebiyi, J. S. (2005). Determinants of agricultural credit supply to farmers in the Niger Delta Area of Nigeria. *Journal of Agriculture and social Research (JASR)*, 5(1), 67-72.
- Ojeaga P., Odejimi O., Okhiku J., & Ojeaga D. (2018). Does commercial bank lending incite growth? The impact of commercial lending on real sector growth in Nigeria. Available:www/http:ssrn.com Accessed: 30th June, 2018
- Olannye, V. I., Maku, E. O., & Adelowokan, O. A. (2023). The relative impact of domestic credit to the private and public sectors on economic growth in Nigeria. *KIU Journal of Social Sciences*, 9(1), 231-241.
- Olusegun A. J., Akintoye I. R., & Dada S. O. (2014). Commercial bank credit and sectoral growth in Sub-Saharan Africa: Evidence from Nigeria. *Global Advanced Research Journal of Management and Business Studies*. 2014; 3(9): 423-431.
- Olowofeso, E. O., Adeleke, A. O., & Udoji, A. O. (2015). Impact of private sector credit on economic growth in Nigeria. *CBN Journal of Applied Statistics*, 6(2), 81-101.
- Olowofeso, O. E., Adeboye, A. A., Adejo, V. T., Bassey, K. J., & Abraham, O. (2017). Agricultural sector credit and output relationship in Nigeria: Evidence from nonlinear ARDL1. *CBN Journal of Applied Statistics (JAS)*, 8(1), 5.
- Oluitan R. O. (2013) Bank credit and economic growth: Evidence from Nigeria. *International Business and Management*. 2012; 5(2):102-110.
- Oni O., Akinlo A. E., & Oladepo E. D. (2014). Impact of bank credit on the real sector: Evidence from Nigeria. *Global Journal of Business Research*. 2014; 8(3): 39-47.
- Onodugo, V. A., Kalu, I. E., & Anowor, O. F. (2013). Financial intermediation and private sector investment in Nigeria. *Research journal of finance and accounting*, 4(12), 47-54.
- Onodugo, V. A., Anowor, O. F., Ukwenu, N. O., & Ibiyam, F. O. (2014). Bank credit and private sector investment: Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Management Sciences*, 3(2), 82-92.
- Onuorah, A. C., & Ozurumba, B. A. (2013). Bank credits: An aid to economic growth in Nigeria. In *Information and Knowledge Management* (Vol. 3, No. 3, pp. 41-50).
- Orji, A. (2012) Bank Savings and Bank Credits in Nigeria: Determinants and Impact on Economic Growth. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues* Vol. 2, No. 3, 2012, pp.357-372.
- Ozili, P. K., Oladipo, O., & Iorember, P. T. (2023). Effect of abnormal increase in credit supply on economic growth in Nigeria. *African Journal of Economic and Management Studies*, 14(4), 583-599.
- Porter (1966): The Promotion of the Banking Habit and Economic Development. *Journal of Development Studies*, Vol. 2, No. 4
- Robinson, J. (1952). The rate of interest and other essays. The Generalization of the General Theory/MacMillan.
- Shan, J. (2005). Does financial development 'lead' economic growth? A vector auto-regression appraisal. *Applied Economics*, 37(12), 1353-1367.
- Schumpeter, J. A. (1911), The theory of economic development: an inquiry into profits, capital, credit, interest and the business cycle, translated from the German by Redvers Opie, New Brunswick (U.S.A) and London (U.K.): Transaction Publishers
- Taiwo, J. N., Alege, P. O., & Olokoyo, F. O. (2016). Microfinancing and Microenterprise Growth in Nigeria. *Lagos Journal of Banking*,

- Finance & Economic*, 3(1), 87-119.
- Toby, A. J., & Dibiah, S. (2022). Financial intermediation and economic growth in Nigeria. *World Journal of Finance and Investment Research* 6(2) 2682-5902
- Tuuli, K. (2002). Do efficient banking sectors accelerate economic growth in transition countries? (December 19, 2022). *BOFIT Discussion Paper*, (14)
- Ubesie, C. M., Echekoba, N., Chris-Ejiogu, U. G. & Ananwude, A. C. (2019). Sectoral Allocation of Deposit Money Banks' Credit and the Growth of Nigerian Real Economy: A Disaggregated Analysis (2008Q1 – 2017Q4). *Journal of Economics, Management and Trade* 22(1): 1-22.
- Udoka C. O., Mbat D. O., & Duke, S. B. (2015). The effect of commercial banks' credit on agricultural production in Nigeria. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*. 2015; 4(1): 1-10.
- Uzomba, P. C., Chukwu, S. N., Jumbo, G. A., & Nwankwo, N. U. (2014). An inquiring into the impact of deposit money banks' loans/advances on agricultural sector in Nigeria; 1980–2011. *International Review of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 7(2), 130-139.
- Yakubu, Z., & Afoi, A. Y. (2014). An analysis of commercial banks' credit on economic growth in Nigeria. *Current Research Journal of Economic Theory*, 6(2), 11-15.
- Yerima, O. W., & Idris, M. Effect of Banking Credits on Economic Growth: Evidence from Nigeria.
- Zang, H., & Kim, Y. C. (2007). Does financial development precede growth? Robinson and Lucas might be right. *Applied Economics Letters*, 14(1), 15-19.